

Supplement. eResults: sensitivity analyses

This supplement reports the revision sensitivity analyses summarized in the main text; their methods are in Supplement eMethods (S4). Every number is regenerated by `make phase2b`. The design-based primary analyses remain those in the main Results and Table 2; the analyses here probe item non-response, the SHAP attribution algorithm, the structure of the intersectional strata, and generalization to an earlier survey year.

Per-predictor missingness

Every predictor was present in the 2024 analytic file and the screening outcome was complete; only household income carried appreciable item non-response. In the primary established-eligible cohort income was missing for 15.5% of records (16.6% weighted); every other predictor was missing in fewer than 3.4% (Table S5.1). The full 45-to-75 cohort showed the same pattern (income 14.9% unweighted, 15.9% weighted). Missing predictors were imputed inside each training fold with the survey-weighted mode (categorical) or median (age), so no held-out record informed its own imputation, and income drove the fractions of missing information in the imputation sensitivity below.

Table S5.1. Per-predictor missingness, established-eligible 50-to-75 cohort (n = 200,471 before listwise steps).

Predictor	n missing	% unweighted	% weighted
Household income	31,104	15.5	16.6
Metropolitan status	6,762	3.4	2.4
Urban/rural status	6,762	3.4	2.4
Insurance	5,664	2.8	3.2
Employment	1,572	0.8	0.9
Marital status	1,517	0.8	0.8
Education	765	0.4	0.5
Race/ethnicity	0	0.0	0.0
Sex	0	0.0	0.0
Census region	0	0.0	0.0

Predictor	n missing	% unweighted	% weighted
Age	0	0.0	0.0

Multiple-imputation sensitivity for the interaction tests

The primary pipeline used a single survey-weighted imputation inside each fold, which understates the uncertainty from item non-response in income. We refit the four pre-specified product-term tests across 20 chained-equation imputations and pooled them by Rubin’s rules (Table S5.2). The employment-by-income term stayed positive and clearly nonzero after imputation (pooled log-odds 0.055; 95% CI, 0.034 to 0.075; $P < .001$), attenuated from the single-imputation estimate and carrying a high fraction of missing information (0.54) driven by income. The interaction therefore persisted after imputation, but its direction depended on the scalar employment encoding: the full-categorical re-analysis below found the doubly-disadvantaged corner sub-additive, so the positive scalar term does not support a super-additive reading. The education-by-income term, negative under single imputation, was no longer separable from zero once income was multiply imputed (pooled -0.006 ; 95% CI, -0.015 to 0.003 ; $P = .18$; fraction of missing information 0.53), so the apparent diminishing-returns pattern there is fragile to how missing income is handled and we do not rest any claim on it. The age-by-employment and education-by-race/ethnicity terms had low fractions of missing information (0.10 and 0.03) and did not change conclusion. For age-by-employment the imputation interval excludes zero while the design-based primary test does not; the point estimates agree (0.035 vs 0.030) and the difference is the standard error, which carries primary sampling unit clustering in the design-based test and does not in the model-based pooled test. The pooled standard errors here are model-based and omit that clustering, so these intervals are not interchangeable with the design-based primary tests in the main text.

Table S5.2. Multiple-imputation (M = 20) versus single-imputation product-term tests.

Interaction pair	MI pooled log-odds (95% CI)	P	FMI	Single-imputation design-based log-odds (95% CI)
Age x employment	0.035 (0.009 to 0.061)	.008	0.10	0.030 (-0.029 to 0.096)

Interaction pair	MI pooled log-odds (95% CI)	P	FMI	Single-imputation design-based log-odds (95% CI)
Employment × income	0.055 (0.034 to 0.075)	<.001	0.54	0.107 (0.075 to 0.143)
Education × income	-0.006 (-0.015 to 0.003)	.18	0.53	-0.029 (-0.044 to -0.013)
Education × race/ethnicity	-0.011 (-0.032 to 0.011)	.32	0.03	-0.008 (-0.058 to 0.039)

FMI, fraction of missing information. P is the Rubin pooled two-sided value (model-based). The single-imputation column is the design-based primary test (coefficient and 95% CI; its P is in the main text). Coefficients are on the log-odds scale (multiplicative interaction), not additive RERI. The positive employment-by-income coefficient reflects the scalar encoding, in which employment is coded disadvantage-increasing and income advantage-increasing; the full-categorical re-analysis (Table S5.7) found the doubly-disadvantaged combination sub-additive.

Multiplicative interaction re-analysis: encoding robustness (employment × income)

The single positive product term in the primary tests, employment with income, warranted a closer look because the two predictors carry opposite valences on their scalar codings. Employment entered as disadvantage-increasing (not employed versus employed), whereas income entered as advantage-increasing (band 1, lowest, to band 7, highest). On scales that run in opposite directions a positive product-term coefficient marks a joint effect smaller than the sum of its parts, not larger, so the sign alone does not establish super-additive risk. We re-examined the pair two ways (Table S5.7).

First, we recomputed the four pre-specified scalar product terms with corrected inference: P values came from Wald tests on design-based bootstrap standard errors rather than from the bootstrap percentile, which floored near the reciprocal of the resample count and could not resolve very small values. The employment-by-income

term was 0.107 (95% CI, 0.075 to 0.143; $z = 6.20$; $P = 5.7 \times 10^{-10}$), education-by-income was -0.029 (95% CI, -0.044 to -0.013 ; $P = 5.6 \times 10^{-4}$), age-by-employment was 0.030 (95% CI, -0.028 to 0.093; $P = .34$), and education-by-race/ethnicity was -0.008 (95% CI, -0.060 to 0.040; $P = .77$). The point estimates reproduce the design-based primary tests; only the P values change.

Second, we re-encoded both predictors fully categorically to read the joint effect at the doubly-disadvantaged corner directly. Employment was split into three groups, employed (reference), precarious (out of work or unable to work), and not in the labor force (retired, homemaker, or student), so that retirees, who delayed least, were no longer grouped with adults out of work, who delayed most. Income entered as its seven bands with the highest band as the reference. On complete cases ($n = 168,657$) every precarious-by-income coefficient was negative, and the precarious-by-lowest-income cell was -1.264 (95% CI, -1.819 to -0.625 ; $P = 6.3 \times 10^{-5}$). A joint Wald test on the six precarious-by-income terms was significant ($\chi^2 = 42.04$; $df = 6$; $P = 1.8 \times 10^{-7}$), with every block coefficient negative, so the combined burden of precarious employment and low income fell below the additive prediction. The doubly-disadvantaged corner was sub-additive. The positive scalar coefficient therefore reflected the opposite valences of the two codings, not a synergy between joblessness and low income, and it does not support super-additive compounding. This sub-additive reading agrees with the MAIHDA result below, where additive main effects explained 91.5% of the between-stratum variance and left an 8.5% non-additive residual.

Table S5.7. Employment-by-income interaction under two encodings (established-eligible 50-to-75 cohort). Scalar specification: the four pre-specified product terms, coefficients on the log-odds scale, P from Wald tests on design-based bootstrap standard errors ($B = 400$). Full-categorical specification: employment in three groups crossed with income in seven bands, complete cases ($n = 168,657$).

Specification and term	Coefficient (95% CI)	P
Scalar, employment × income	0.107 (0.075 to 0.143)	5.7×10^{-10}
Scalar, education × income	-0.029 (-0.044 to -0.013)	5.6×10^{-4}
Scalar, age × employment	0.030 (-0.028 to 0.093)	.34
Scalar, education × race/ethnicity	-0.008 (-0.060 to 0.040)	.77

Specification and term	Coefficient (95% CI)	P
Full-categorical, precarious × lowest income	-1.264 (-1.819 to -0.625)	6.3×10^{-5}
Full-categorical, joint Wald (precarious × income)	$\chi^2 = 42.04, df = 6$	1.8×10^{-7}

Interventional versus path-dependent SHAP, and predictor association

Recomputing the global summary with interventional TreeSHAP against a weighted background changed the per-predictor magnitudes only slightly and left the ordering essentially intact (Spearman correlation 0.96 between the two rankings; Table S5.3). Education stayed the leading social determinant under both algorithms, ahead of income, so the headline ordering does not depend on the credit-allocation rule even though education and income are the most correlated determinant pair (bias-corrected Cramér V 0.27; Table S5.4). The one clear change was insurance, which fell from sixth to eighth under the interventional calculation, the expected direction if path-dependent SHAP had credited it partly through correlated paths. The association matrix shows the mechanical correlations one would expect, metropolitan with urban status (0.63) and age with employment (correlation ratio 0.60), alongside the weaker correlations among the substantive social determinants that the model has to separate.

Table S5.3. Grouped mean absolute SHAP by attribution algorithm (primary cohort).

Predictor	Path-dependent	Interventional	Rank (path → interventional)
Education	0.317	0.351	1 → 1
Age	0.310	0.299	2 → 3
Income	0.291	0.302	3 → 2
Employment	0.229	0.237	4 → 4
Marital status	0.181	0.170	5 → 5

Predictor	Path-dependent	Interventional	Rank (path → interventional)
Insurance	0.134	0.103	6 → 8
Race/ethnicity	0.121	0.121	7 → 6
Census region	0.105	0.107	8 → 7
Sex	0.067	0.066	9 → 9
Metropolitan status	0.037	0.037	10 → 10
Urban/rural status	0.014	0.012	11 → 11

Table S5.4. Predictor association matrix (eligible 50-to-75, unweighted complete pairs). Bias-corrected Cramér V for categorical pairs; correlation ratio (eta) for age against each categorical predictor. Columns 1 to 11 correspond to the numbered variables in the first column.

Variable										1	1
1. Income	1.0	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.2
2. Education	0.2	1.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0
3. Insurance	0.1	0.1	1.0	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1
4. Race/ethnicity	0.1	0.1	0.1	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.1
5. Sex	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
6. Employment	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	1.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.6
7. Marital status	0.2	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.2
8. Metropolitan	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.6	0.0	0.0
9. Urban/rural	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.6	1.0	0.0	0.0
10. Census region	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.0
11. Age	0.2	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.6	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0

Multilevel analysis of the intersectional strata (MAIHDA)

We fit a two-level logistic model with a random intercept over the intersectional strata formed by crossing education, income, race/ethnicity, and sex, following the multilevel analysis of individual heterogeneity and discriminatory accuracy. Crossing the four predictors gave 335 occupied strata in the established-eligible cohort (median 98 records per stratum, range 1 to 11,657), fit on the 169,042 complete-case records (31,429 dropped, almost all for missing income). The model was unweighted: it describes the structure of the strata and complements the survey-weighted predictive model rather than substituting for it.

A null model with only the random intercept placed the between-stratum variance at 0.222 on the logit scale, for a variance partition coefficient of 6.3%. Most of the variance in delay sat within strata, not between them. Adding the additive main effects of the four predictors reduced the between-stratum variance to 0.019, a proportional change in variance of 91.5%, so additive main effects accounted for almost all of the between-stratum variance and left a non-additive intersectional residual of 8.5%. Assigning each adult the mean delay of their own stratum discriminated with a model-free AUC of 0.619, below the 0.698 of the survey-weighted predictive model, so the intersectional strata alone separated delayed from up-to-date adults less well than the individual-level determinants.

We estimated the model by variational Bayes (the intended primary estimator, with the fixed effects scaled). The null model, on which the variance partition coefficient depends, converged with a non-degenerate variance. The adjusted model did not meet the formal variational convergence tolerance, though it returned a stable, non-degenerate between-stratum variance on repeated starts, so we report the proportional change in variance with that caveat; the variance partition coefficient rests only on the converged null model and is unaffected. A maximum a posteriori cross-check collapsed the adjusted between-stratum variance to the boundary (near zero), a known degeneracy of the Laplace approximation when many strata are small, so it did not corroborate the proportional change numerically and we report it for transparency only (Table S5.5). Variational Bayes slightly underestimates variances relative to Markov chain Monte Carlo, so the 8.5% non-additive residual is, if anything, a conservative estimate. The small between-stratum share and the large proportional change together place most of the social patterning of delay in the additive main effects, with little left for non-additive intersectional interaction, consistent with the product-term tests in which no pair combined more than additively.

Table S5.5. MAIHDA of the intersectional strata (education × income × race/ethnicity × sex; established-eligible 50-to-75 cohort; n = 169,042 complete cases across 335 strata). Variational Bayes is the primary estimator; the maximum a posteriori fit is a cross-check.

Estimator	Null between-stratum variance	VPC, %	Adjusted between-stratum variance	PCV, %
Variational Bayes (primary)	0.222	6.3	0.019	91.5
Maximum a posteriori (cross-check)	0.125	3.7	~0 (boundary)	100.0

VPC, variance partition coefficient, the between-stratum share of the latent variance with the within-stratum logistic variance fixed at $\pi^2/3 = 3.29$; PCV, proportional change in variance, the share of the between-stratum variance explained by the additive main effects. The maximum a posteriori adjusted variance collapsed to the boundary, a Laplace degeneracy with many small strata, so its 100% PCV is an artifact and does not corroborate the variational-Bayes value; the variational-Bayes null variance is non-degenerate and identifies the reported VPC. The variational-Bayes adjusted fit did not meet the formal convergence tolerance but returned a stable, non-degenerate variance on repeated starts, so the PCV is reported with that caveat.

External temporal validation on BRFSS 2022

We applied each final 2024 model, with no refitting and no recalibration, to the 2022 survey, the most recent prior even-numbered year in which the colorectal screening core was administered nationwide. Discrimination transported well. In the primary established-eligible cohort the weighted AUC on 2022 data was 0.707 (95% CI, 0.702 to 0.713), matching rather than falling below the internal 2024 estimate of 0.698; in the full cohort it was 0.755 (95% CI, 0.751 to 0.760) against 0.737 internally (Table S5.6). Calibration in the large drifted in the expected direction. Weighted screening delay was higher in 2022 than in 2024, 27.7% versus 24.8% in the established-eligible cohort and 33.8% versus 29.8% in the full cohort, so a model fixed to 2024 under-predicted in 2022 and the calibration intercept turned positive (0.20 and 0.32) while the calibration slope stayed near one (1.03 and 1.10). The higher 2022 delay is consistent with that year sitting closer to the 2021 lowering of the screening age to 45, which leaves more recently eligible adults behind on testing. Because recalibration was withheld by design, this is a test of transportability rather than a refit: the risk ordering learned in 2024 held

in an independent survey year, while the absolute risk level tracked the secular change in measured delay.

Table S5.6. External temporal validation. Each 2024 model applied to BRFSS 2022 with no retraining and no recalibration; internal 2024 values shown for reference. Weighted AUC 95% CIs from the design-based bootstrap (primary sampling units within strata) on the relevant survey year.

Cohort and year	Analytic n	Weighted delay, %	Weighted AUC (95% CI)	Weighted Brier	Cal. intercept	Cal. slope
Established-eligible, 2024 internal	200,471	24.8	0.698 (0.691 to 0.704)	0.166	0.00	1.00
Established-eligible, 2022 external	196,213	27.7	0.707 (0.702 to 0.713)	0.177	0.20	1.03
Full, 2024 internal	227,647	29.8	0.737 (0.731 to 0.743)	0.175	0.00	0.99
Full, 2022 external	222,091	33.8	0.755 (0.751 to 0.760)	0.184	0.32	1.10